

APPLICATION OF DATA MINING AND MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES IN HIGH PERFORMANCE SPORTS

Sabrina Alves de Queiroz^{1*}, Cláudia Maria Goulart¹, Raphael Lopes Olegário^{1,2}

¹Faculty of Physical Education, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil.

²Faculty of Medicine, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil.

*e-mail: sabrinalvesq@gmail.com

Introduction: The use of artificial intelligence (AI), data mining, and statistical modeling in high-performance sports has become recurrent in recent decades. The ongoing and exponential increase of computer processing power has further accelerated the ability to analyze big data (i.e., data sets that are too large or complex to be dealt with by traditional data-processing application software), and indeed, computers are increasingly taking charge of the deeper analysis of data sets through means of AI. **Aim:** This review summarizes research and presents computational tool-related data adopted in high-performance sports. **Methods:** This study adopted a qualitative synthesis model based on a literature review with consultation of primary studies published in specialized scientific journals and subsequent categorization of the data. **Results:** The search for studies obtained from electronic databases, at first, resulted in $\sum n = 97$ studies. After the initial screening process, it resulted in $\sum n = 55$. Then, after the full reading, carried out by two reviewers, the full reading process resulted in $\sum n = 8$. **Discussion:** From the studies included in the final analysis, there was a predominance of technologies associated with exergame-type interventions (i.e., technology-driven physical activities, such as video game play, that require participants to be physically active or exercise in order to play the game). In addition, innovation, design, and the application of technology to competitive sport are of paramount importance to athletes optimizing their best possible performance in the future. **Conclusion:** It was possible to identify a certain pattern of adoption of digital technologies applied to high-performance sports, with a greater recurrence of technological technologies encouraged in computer interfaces such as exergames.

Keywords: technology; sport; data mining; machine learning; athletes.

Acknowledgments: We thank the Faculty of Physical Education - University of Brasília for the opportunity to undertake the studies that helped in the elaboration of this research.